

Literature review on values considered in decision-making contexts at local level

General procedure for coding the selected references

1. Design and elaboration of a table of literature based on criteria proposed by the decision-making typology.

Table 1 – Assessment criteria and sub-criteria based on the Decision-Making Typology (DMT) for the IPBES Values Assessment

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA		SUB-CRITERIA		CLASSIFICATION BY SUB-CRITERIA				
EXPRESSION OF VALUES IN DECISION MAKING	Categories of values	Relational values		Indigenous values/worldviews				
		Instrumental values						
		Intrinsic values						
	Purpose of valuations	Informative e.g., process seeks to (trans)form values and raise awareness						
Decisive e.g., enabling effective actions on translation of [plural] values into policy and practice								
Technical e.g., implementation of policies, plans, programmes and/or instruments								
DECISION-MAKING TYPOLOGY (DMT)	Types of decision makers (Level 1)	Public actors						
		Private actors						
		Civil society actors						
	Types of decisions (Level 1)	Political decision-making						
		Economic decision-making						
		Socio-environmental decision-making						
	Types of interactions among actors in decision-making (Level 2)	Command						
		Trade						
		Conflict						
		Cooperation		Reciprocity				
	Applying to different contexts (Level 3)	Spatial scale of the decision			Complementarity			
					Territorial integrity			
					Local			
		Internal processes	Rulemaking (purpose, forms of interaction)			National		
						International		
Learning					Promoting inclusiveness			
					Use and/or inclusion of ILK and practices			
		Influence of heuristics						
		Emotional associations e.g., sense of place, spirituality						
		Choosing cheap options; coordination between stakeholders						
		Length of decision-making process						

				Institutions involved	Formal institutions at national level (laws, policies, agreements, regulations)
					Formal institutions acting at local level (e.g., local policies)
					Informal (beliefs, attitudes, social networks, customary norms)
				Resources available for these decisions e.g., size of budgets, personnel	
				Effectiveness or monitoring the implementation of the decision	
	Decision outcomes	New modes of environmental governance over nature/NCP			
		Planning for use of natural assets and NCP			
		Sustainable management of nature/NCP			
		Planning for use of natural assets and NCP			
		Knowledge generation	Enhancing capacities of stakeholders i.e., it can help stakeholders to improve their participation in communication and negotiations.		

2. Identification and score of trial references to assess score reliability, replicability and to standardize the scoring criteria.

Table 2 – Effectiveness rating scale of sub-criteria and outcomes

Effectiveness rating scale of value types articulated and decision-making typology in final decision		
Scarce (S)	Moderate (M)	High (H)
0-30%	30-70%	70-100%
Effectiveness rating scale of decision-making length		
>3 years	2-3 years	<2 years
Relevance to impact on progress towards achieving selected SDG/targets		
Scarce (S)	Moderate (M)	High (H)
0-30%	30-70%	70-100%

N.A.: Not applicable n/a: information not available

3. Grouping outcomes into categories based on:

- a. *stakeholders*: who is affected by the decisions and who has the power to influence their outcome
- b. *process outcomes* (e.g., management, planning and/or governance of rivers, coasts, urban forestry areas, protected areas).

4. Assessment of decisions according to their relative impact across NCPs and SDGs, following the criteria below:

- a. Direction of impact
- b. Positive or negative, and the relative scale of the impact
- c. Impact on the UN SDG outcomes/outcome group
- d. Co-benefits
- e. Adverse side effects

Table 3 – NCPs categories

NCPs	MATERIAL (M), NON-MATERIAL (NM) AND REGULATING (R) NCPs
1	Habitat creation and maintenance (R)
2	Pollination and dispersal of seeds and other propagules (R)
3	Regulation of air quality (R)
4	Regulation of climate (R)
5	Regulation of ocean acidification (R)
6	Regulation of freshwater quantity, location and timing (R)
7	Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality (R)
8	Formation, protection and decontamination of soils and sediments (R)
9	Regulation of hazards and extreme events (R)
10	Regulation of detrimental organisms and biological processes (R)
11	Energy (M)
12	Food and feed (M)
13	Materials, companionship and labour (M)
14	Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources (M)
15	Learning and inspiration (NM)
16	Physical and psychological experiences (NM)
17	Supporting identities (NM)
18	Maintenance of options (R, M, NM)

Table 4 – Selected Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with their specific targets

SDGs	TARGET ACCORDING TO EACH SDG
SDG related to socioeconomic conditions	
SDG # 1 No poverty	1.1 Eradicate extreme poverty
	1.2 Halve the proportion of people in poverty
	1.4 Ensure that all have equal rights to economic resources
	1.5 Build the resilience of the poor
SDG # 2 Zero hunger	2.1 End hunger and ensure access to food all year round
	2.3 Double productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers
	2.4 Ensure sustainable food production systems
	2.5 Maintain the genetic diversity of seeds, cultivated plants and farmed animals and their related wild species
SDG # 3 Good health & well-being	3.2 End preventable deaths of newborns and children under 5 years of age
	3.3 End AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria and neglected tropical diseases
	3.4 Reduce premature mortality from non-communicable diseases
	3.9 Reduce the number of deaths and illnesses from water and soil pollution

SDG # 4 Quality education	4.5 Eliminate gender disparities in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for the vulnerable
	4.7 Ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development
SDG # 5 Gender equality	5.1 End all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere
	5.5 Ensure women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision making in political, economic and public life
	5.A Access to ownership and control over land and other forms of property, financial services, inheritance and natural resources
SDG # 10 Reduced Inequalities	10.2 Promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status
	10.4 Adopt policies, especially fiscal, wage and social protection policies, and progressively achieve greater equality
	10.3 Ensure equal opportunity and reduce inequalities of outcome, including by eliminating discriminatory laws, policies and practices and promoting appropriate legislation, policies and action in this regard
SDG # 11 Sustainable cities and communities	11.3 Enhance inclusive and sustainable urbanization and capacity for participatory, integrated and sustainable human settlement planning and management
	11.4 Protect and safeguard cultural and natural heritage
	11.5 Reduce deaths and the number of people affected by disasters
	11.6 Reduce the adverse per capita environmental impact of cities
	11.7 Provide universal access to green and public spaces
SDG # 16 Peace, justice & strong institutions	16.6 Develop effective, accountable and transparent institutions at all levels
	16.7 Ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels
	16.8 Broaden and strengthen the participation of developing countries in the institutions of global governance
	16.b Promote and enforce non-discriminatory laws and policies for sustainable development
SDG related to nature and NCP	
SDG # 6 Clean water and sanitation	6.3 Improve water quality
	6.4 Increase water-use efficiency across all sectors and ensure sustainable withdrawals
	6.5 Implement integrated water resources management
	6.6 Protect and restore water-related ecosystems, including mountains, forests, wetlands, rivers, aquifers and lakes
SDG # 13 Climate action	13.1 Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters
	13.2 Integrate climate change measures into policies, strategies and planning
	13.3 Improve education, awareness-raising and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning
	13a Mobilize US\$100 billion/year for mitigation by developing countries
	13b Raise capacity for effective climate change-related planning and management
SDG # 14 Life below water	14.1 Prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution
	14.2 Sustainably manage and protect marine and coastal ecosystems
	14.3 Minimize and address the impacts of ocean acidification,
	14.4 Regulate harvesting and end overfishing,
	14.5 Conserve at least 10 per cent of coastal and marine areas
	14.6 Prohibit subsidies which contribute to overcapacity and overfishing
	14.7 Increase economic benefits from sustainable use of marine resources
	15.1 Ensure conservation, restoration and sustainable use of terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems and their services
	15.2 Promote the implementation of sustainable management of all types of forests, restore degraded forests and halt deforestation

SDG # 15 Life on land	15.3 Combat desertification and restore degraded land and soil
	15.4 Ensure the conservation of mountain ecosystems, including their biodiversity
	15.5 Reduce degradation of natural habitats, halt the loss of biodiversity, protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species
	15.6 Promote fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources
	15.7 End poaching and trafficking of protected species of flora and fauna
	15.8 Prevent the introduction and reduce the impact of invasive alien species
	15.9 Integrate ecosystem and biodiversity values into national and local planning, development processes, poverty reduction strategies and accounts
	15.a Increase financial resources to conserve and sustainably use biodiversity and ecosystems
	15.b Mobilize resources to finance sustainable forest management

5. Identification of groups of decision outcomes at the local scale on different geographic locations: ‘new modes of environmental governance’; ‘planning for use of natural assets and NCP’; ‘sustainable management of nature/NCP’; ‘new policies, plans, programmes, or instruments’; ‘knowledge generation’.